

A STUDY OF THE ATTITUDE OF PRIMARY TEACHER TOWARDS THEIR GENDER AND EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

Industrialists, Doctors, engineers, scientists, Economist have played significant role but all these personalities educate by only and only teachers. Students always follows as well as imitate the teachers behave, talks, personality, dressing since, working style etc. Is there any effect of this system on teacher's attitudes? 1979 and Schofield,1981 have found a significance correlation between teacher attitude and students achievement. In this paper the researcher humble tried to check how present situation affected the teacher's attitudes. One hundred and fifty eight (158) primary school teachers randomly selected from Bharuch district for this study. For the analysis and interpretation of data and testing of the hypotheses' test was used. The teacher attitude inventory was administered to the teachers in each of the randomly selected primary schools involved in the study from Bharuch District.

Keywords: Attitude, Primary Teacher, Experience

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are creating national integration, learning society, create and generate new knowledge. Nation's progress is intimately connected with teachers work because Globalization poses fundamental challenges for all area of education. Teacher should stand and alert for coming challenges. Industrialists, Doctors, engineers, scientists, Economist have played significant role but all these personalities educate by only and only teachers. So teachers may be solid pillars of these. The effective attitudes and actions employed by teachers by teachers ultimately can make a positive difference on the lives on their student and classroom teaching.

Students always follows as well as imitate the teachers behave, talks, personality, dressing since, working style etc. teachers full commitment to his profession student get good contact with content, well adjusted, self-motivated and respectful nature. For all these type of personality development, to shape the future of pupils a teacher must have must have such professional attitudes.

Today in our society teacher had a endless challenges. We also believe that fact the primary teachers got only 2500 Rs. Per month. They didn't get pension and incentives with comparison of other permanent teachers. Today's teachers suffer from lack of confidence, low salary, no protection and they not receive the status and respect from society. Are the teachers satisfied with this system?

Is there any effect of this system on teacher's attitudes? Many researches have held the view that their important relationship between the attitude of teacher and the effectiveness or quality of their teaching. Aiken,1970 and Larson,1983 shows that teacher Attitudes influence on students attitude, Begley, 1979 and Schofield,1981 have found a significance correlation between teacher attitude and students achievement. So here researcher humble tried to check how present situation affected the teacher's attitudes.

OBJECTIVES

- To study the Attitudes of Primary school teachers.
- To study the effect of Gender on the attitudes of primary school teachers.
- To study the effect of experience on the attitude of Primary school teachers.
- To study the effect of interaction of Gender and Experience on the attitudes of Primary school teachers.

HYPOTHESES

In this study following hypotheses have been formulated for testing the objectives.

- There will be no significant difference between mean scores of male and female teachers.

- There will be no significant difference between means scores of above 10 years' experience teachers and below 10 years' experience teachers.
- There will be no significant effect of interaction of Gender and experience on Attitudes of teachers.

Methodology Participants

One hundred and fifty eight (158) primary school teachers randomly selected from Bharuch district for this study. 49 (31.01%) were male and 109 (68.9%) were female and 120 were above 10 yrs of experience and 38 were below 10 years of experience.

Instruments:

Teacher Attitude was measured by the Teacher Attitude Inventory by S.P.Ahluwalia. It is consisting of six sub scale viz. teaching profession, classroom teaching, child centred practice, educational process, pupile and teacher. A five point likert type scale consisting 90 items were used. Each scale has 15 statement that pertain to a particular aspect of prospective and practicing teachers attitudes. Reliability for this inventory was 0.79 and coefficient corrected was 0.70.

Procedure:

The teacher attitude inventory was administered to the teachers in each of the randomly selected primary schools involved in the study from Bharuch District. In the schools involved in this study, the participants were assured of the anonymity and confidentiality of their responses.

Data Analysis:

For the analysis and interpretation of data and testing of the hypotheses' test was used. The independent variables are experience: above 10 years and gender: Male and female. Scores of attitudes towards profession is taken as dependent variable.

Results:

The results obtained from the analysis are presented in following tables. Tables showing mean, S.D. and 't' scores of attitude towards teaching profession of Primary School Teachers.

Table 1.

Significance of difference between Mean Scores of Primary Teachers' attitude with respects to Gender.

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	40	243.3	40.4	3.69
Female	109	266.8	35.9	

Above table reveals that 't' test value of male and female primary teacher's attitude is significant at 0.01 level.

Table 2.

Significance of difference between mean scores of primary teachers' attitude with respects to Qualification

Qualification	N	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Above 10 years	120	242.43	36.3	2.92
Below 10 years	38	249.07	40.6	

Above table reveals that 't' test value with respect to qualification of male and female primary teacher's attitude is significant at 0.01 levels.

Table 3.

Significance of difference between mean score of gender wise primary teachers' attitude with respects to various scales of teaching profession

Attitude Subscale	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Teaching Profession	Male	49	43.26	8.14	0.09
	Female	109	43.39	8.06	
Classroom Teaching	Male	49	42.18	8.14	0.97
	Female	109	40.94	7.09	
Child Centered Practice	Male	49	38.77	6.04	0.78
	Female	109	39.62	6.34	
Educational Process	Male	49	41.36	8.39	3.35
	Female	109	43.11	7.23	
Pupils	Male	49	39.04	6.30	3.74
	Female	109	42.91	8.75	
Teachers	Male	49	38.65	9.26	1.32

	Female	109	39.37	7.27	
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On the scale of teaching profession male and female teachers of primary school having significant difference in educational process and pupil centered attitude. But Teaching profession, classroom Teaching, Child centered Practice and Teacher wise attitude are not significant in both male and female.

Table 4.

Significance of difference between mean scores of experience wise primary teachers' attitude with respects to various scales of teaching profession.

Attitude Subscale	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Teaching Profession	Above 10 Years	120	42.84	8.04	0.09
	Below 10 Years	38	45.97	9.08	
Classroom Teaching	Above 10 Years	120	41.10	7.16	0.97
	Below 10 Years	38	44.03	9.37	
Child Centered Practice	Above 10 Years	120	39.27	6.32	0.78
	Below 10 Years	38	39.60	6.07	
Educational Process	Above 10 Years	120	42.65	7.40	3.35
	Below 10 Years	38	42.31	8.40	
Pupils	Above 10 Years	120	37.84	7.10	3.74
	Below 10 Years	38	40.60	10.74	
Teachers	Above 10 Years	120	38.70	7.78	1.32
	Below 10 Years	38	40.55	9.38	

On the scale of attitude male and female teachers of primary school having significant difference in teaching profession, classroom teaching, teachers and pupil centered attitude. But child centered practice and educational process wise attitudes are not significant in both male and female.

FINDINGS

Gender and experience have overall effect on attitude of primary school teachers. Gender has also effect on some attitude scale like educational process and pupil centered attitude.

Significant difference in teaching profession, classroom teaching, teacher and pupil centered attitude is clear evidence of effect of experience on primary teacher's attitude.

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